

Energy, Society and Sociodemographic Constraints Nexus: Development and Future Prospects

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Abstract

To overcome the challenges faced by the energy sector, policymakers need to prioritize the development of strategic policies that promote the adoption of waste-to-energy technologies, Tidal energy, solar power systems, and wind farms. These policies should emphasize the integration of renewable energy sources into the existing energy infrastructure, ensuring a more sustainable and resilient energy supply for urban areas. The study underscores the importance of collaboration between various stakeholders, including government bodies, private sector entities, and local communities. By fostering partnerships and creating incentives, it becomes possible to mobilize resources and expertise towards the implementation of renewable energy projects. This collaboration would not only address the energy crisis but also contribute to job creation and overall socioeconomic development. Proper utilization of renewable energy resources can resolve the dilemma of energy crises in the country. According to our results, solar stood first in the overall ranking followed by Tidal, waste-to-energy, and wind energies. Solar performed better in indigenous manufacturing and development, resource potential, and technological development. Pakistan has abundant green energy resources which could be utilized by the formation of a proper policy roadmap and mitigation of policy pathways to overcome the hazardous dependence on fossil fuels for energy requirements. The implementation of policies adopted should be assured to achieve energy sustainability.

Index Terms: Economic Growth, Indigenous Manufacturing and Development, Infrastructure, Renewable Resources, Strategic Assessment.

I. INTRODUCTION

Strategic assessment of renewable energy technology to benefit society in energy-deficient third-world countries incorporate parameters that are slightly different in contrast to developed countries of the world [1]. The facilities that are termed as necessities in any developed country are predominantly assumed as luxuries for residents of many low-income third-world countries. Lack of these necessities includes proper sanitation facilities, clean drinking water, proper transportation framework, electricity supply for the domestic sector, a clean environment for healthy growth of individuals, and medical facilities [2]. Pakistan as a third-world low-income country with a population of 22.6 million, lacks these necessities for the majority of its population. The total primary energy supplies are 81 million Tonne of Oil Equivalent (TOE) of which only 1% is supplied from renewable electricity and 10% from hydroelectricity. The other major contributors are 21% oil, 33% renewable, 10% LPG imports, and 18% coal. The net consumption is 52 million TOE. The major consumers of energy are the industrial sector with a 37% share transportation sector with a 30% share and the domestic sector with a 24% share. The indigenous oil refiners are producing around 10 million tonnes. The total petroleum product consumption was 17 million tonnes in 2019 – 2020 compared to 22 Million tonnes in 2014-15. The major consumers of

petroleum products are the transportation sector with 81 % share followed by industrial 7.17% and the power sector 9% share in 2019-2020. The consumption of petroleum products in transportation increased from 51% in 2014-15 to 81 % in 2019-20 whereas the power sector consumed 41% in 2014–15 which decreased to 9% in 2019-20. The industrial sector consumed 7% in 2014-15. The coal consumption is 25 million tonnes of which 43% is consumed by the power sector 24% for cement production and 32% for brick kilns. The coal consumption increased from 8.7 million tonnes in 2014-15 to 25 million tonnes in 2019-20. The indigenous production is around 9 million tonnes with 16 million tonnes supplied from imports. The annual growth rate of indigenous production is 50% compared to 8% in 2014-15. The growth rate for imports of coal was 60% in 2014-15 which reduced to 5% in 2019 -20. The total electricity generation is 128673 GWh of which 26% is contributed by hydel resources, 20% by coal, 20% by gas, 16% from RLNG, 8% nuclear, 7% oil, and 3% renewable resources in 2019-20. The total consumption is 108371 GWh. The domestic sector consumes 52% electricity followed by 24% industrial 9% agriculture and 7% consumption in commercial sector 2019-20. The industrial sector consumed 29% in 2015-16 with a 48% share of the domestic sector. The total installed capacity of renewable resources except hydro is 1921 MW in 2019-20. The total generation is 4152 GWh from which 705 GWh is supplied by solar, 2882 by wind, and 565 from Bagasse.

Solar energy contributes 17% of the total electricity generation with 70% wind and 13% bagasse share in 2019-20 [3].

In this article, we aim to connect the society, energy, and socio-demographic constraints nexus and propose an applicable model to resolve the underlying crises of energy shortages in the present situation of the country. In this regard we have adopted an integrated SWOT (Strength, Weakness, Opportunity, and Threat) and Growth factors parametric analysis to analyze the potential for an available resource to resolve energy shortages, secondly accessing the growth parameter and finally achieving a proper mitigation strategy selection depending on the results of assessment to develop a proper road map to facilitate the society for its energy needs. The monetization of societal parameters and mitigation strategies are suggested through proper policy incentives.

II. METHODOLOGY

We aim to study the availability, benefits, and opportunities of green technologies, tidal, and energy from municipal solid waste to resolve the issue of energy shortages in large cities of Pakistan. Keeping in view the country's data availability scenario and economic condition a novel approach of integrating SWOT and growth factor parametric analysis using AHP (Analytical Hierarchy Process).

For the underlying issue, we adopt the following sequential methodological operation:

1. The criteria and sub-criteria for AHP were chosen by conducting a SWOT analysis. For SWOT analysis the author has taken the decision in the light of recent literature review.
2. In the next step, the growth factor parametric analysis was undertaken using AHP. For the decision regarding growth factors Delphi approach was adopted for which leading energy specialists of the country were contacted and a detailed questionnaire was asked verbally.
3. The results from the comparison are integrated with the applied approach.

This technique is used for policy development to identify a proper road map for a sustainable energy future. The analysis is properly suited for the underlying issue because of the following reasons:

1. Data availability in some areas of renewable research is limited.
2. Planning objectives according to our study could be rationalized as per the information gathered.
3. The resource available for the country according to need is assessed and discussed.
4. The analysis response criteria are achieved to maximize our opportunities.
5. A proper framework for further policy implications of a particular nation could be visualized.

Growth factors were accessed for each energy scenario according to the following calibrated scales as shown in figure I.

Figure I: Description of Growth Factors and Corresponding Scores

A. Literature Reviewed for SWOT Analysis

A literature survey of the data available was done according to the following strategy:

- Research articles, publication databases, and conference proceedings are thoroughly analyzed.
- Annual reports from national and international agencies were analyzed.

The sources were analyzed from the scenario of a policy framework and prospects for the resource available, social and societal benefits from the resource identified and prioritized. The best resource available to overcome the shortages of electricity supply was deducted. For the research approach, adaption following literature on country-based perspective focused on the Available Energy Resource scenario was considered.

Opportunistic Application of SWOT Analysis is done to identify the untapped potential, technological improvement, and competitive users of energy resources [4]. SWOT is a compatible strategy analysis tool to identify the internal and external assessment criteria for financial and social outcomes of selected research for the country [5]. Energy strategy selection, upgradation of transmission system options, human and institutional capacity building, structural change in the industrial sector, and electricity generation options were analyzed [6]. Sustainable planning strategies should be implemented for the usage of tidal power and energy-efficient green resources. With an adaptation of flexible choices from all stakeholders, a coherence between the exploitation of tidal and climate change policies should be developed [7]. Energy Crises and climate change vulnerability, purchase of 100% Renewable Energy (RE) systems, potential barriers, and forward policy implications should be taken into consideration for a proper road map to develop RE systems [8]. An analytical review was presented for internal and external facts influencing the strategic selection of RE technology [9]. An analytical review of the integrated strategy for evaluation and ranking of renewable technology, and strategy for policy planning for low-cost provision of energy to the industrial, commercial, and domestic sectors is revealed [10]. A detailed review of India's progress in the usage of green energy was studied. Also, a comparison to other countries incapable of renewable development was studied [11]. Fundamental barriers were identified to the solar energy adaptation and policy recommendations were proposed for the utilization of solar energy potential through a detailed review.

The literature analysis prescribed that SWOT analysis is a suitable technique for the underlying issue resolution [12]. Proper usage of available resources in connection with the energy needs of society is a multi-criteria issue [13]. The final impact on society due to the usage of available resources is a multi-dimensional topic to be considered [14].

Analytic Review for power generation potential from municipal solid waste by thermochemical and biochemical processes is addressed in detail [15]. Prospects to supplement the energy needs of the country are summarized.

B. Review of Resources Available

The world is transitioning towards renewable energy for its energy requirements. Renewable energy could be utilized to fulfill the needs of energy-depriving developing countries [16]. Sustainable economic growth could be achieved by proper input of renewable energy in the total energy mix [17]. The increase in the share of renewables in the domestic sector electricity supplies can resolve the financial burdens of electricity bills on end-users [18]. Developing countries are expected to witness a 55% urbanization rate by 2050. The population of Pakistan is expected to become 2-fold in 2050 with almost 50% of the population living in urban areas with increasing energy needs. Municipal solid generation witnessed a growth rate of 2.41% in Pakistan and it is expected to rise with the increase in urban population [19]. Degradation of the environment and public health risks are associated with the

mismanagement of waste in large cities in Pakistan. High population growth rate, improper utilization of available resources, increased economic activity and improper policies are adding up to the issue [20]. Increasing prices of fossil fuel and improper municipal solid waste disposal lead to the generation of energy from waste. The development of effective recycling of organic waste disposal infrastructure is needed. Proper utilization could supplement the energy needs of large cities as used in our neighboring countries like India and China [21]. Pakistan is abundant in all renewable resources. We have shortlisted four resources namely solar, wind, waste-to-energy, and tidal keeping in mind the scenario of our objective to connect the resource availability, maximum benefit to society, and socio-demographic analysis.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Solar, wind, tidal, and waste-to-energy resources are identified for the resolution of the energy dilemma in large cities in Pakistan after an extensive literature survey and SWOT analysis. Seven dependencies are identified as affecting the growth of these resources. The growth factors of these dependencies were analyzed by integrated growth factor and SWOT analysis using the Analytical Hierarchy process. The credit score for each dependency is evaluated through the analysis of data from the reviews of the energy experts of local and international organizations according to figure I for the duration, efficiency, and prospective growth. The combined credit score is calculated for each dependency. The following results are obtained, as can be seen in table I.

In the resource potential criterion, solar gained a credit score of 3 and waste-to-energy gained 2.5 as cities receive high solar insolation, especially in summer. Due to densely populated urban areas, the amount of solid waste available is high. Tidal gains a credit score of 3 as a huge amount of tidal potential is available in the coastal belt of Sindh and Balochistan. In Indigenous manufacturing and development, solar and waste-to-energy gained good results. Influential policies are undertaken by the government for the progress of solar resource potential but still much more is to be done. Tidal gained good results in this criterion as measures are taken by the government to utilize the available tidal resources. In user subsidies criterion solar and waste-to-energy perform better. Tidal gained a score of 2.5. End-user awareness is a critical issue as the illiteracy rate is high. Solar performs better in this section and waste-to-energy resource awareness among end-users in Pakistan still needs proper attention and effort. In technological development, waste-to-energy performs better followed by wind with a good performance in all three sub-criteria. Participation of skilled labor is an important criterion as energy resource exploitation can benefit society largely with job creation as well as the availability of energy. Tidal gained a score of 2.5 in technological development. Solar gained the highest scores in indigenous manufacturing and development. Indigenous manufacturing, user subsidies, and technological development sections perform better in efficiency and duration categories for solar resources. Wind performs better scores in awareness of end-user categories with better performance in efficiency and prospective growth. Waste-

to-energy performs better in resource potential with good potential for prospective growth. Waste-to-energy also performs better in indigenous manufacturing and development, technological development, and participation

of skilled labor. Tidal gained a score of 3 in participation of skilled labor as in undeveloped areas of Sindh and Balochistan province it can provide jobs to skilled and unskilled labor.

Table I: Credit Score for Each Dependency

Resource	Growth Factors	Credit Score for Respective Dependencies		
		Duration	Efficiency	Prospective Growth
Solar	A-Indigenous Manufacturing and Development	1	1	0.5
	B-Resource Potential	1	1	1
	C-Influential Policy Implication	0.5	1	1
	D-User Subsidy	1	1	1
	E-Awareness of End User	1	1	1
	F-Technological Development	1	0.5	1
	G-Participation of Skilled Manpower	0.5	1	1
Wind	A-Indigenous Manufacturing and Development	1	0.5	0.5
	B-Resource Potential	0.5	1	0.5
	C-Influential Policy Implication	0.5	1	0.5
	D-User Subsidy	0.5	0.5	0.5
	E-Awareness of End User	1	0.5	1
	F-Technological Development	1	1	1
	G-Participation of Skilled Manpower	0.5	0.5	0.5
Waste-to-Energy	A-Indigenous Manufacturing and Development	1	0.5	1
	B-Resource Potential	0.5	1	1
	C-Influential Policy Implication	1	1	1
	D-User Subsidy	1	0.5	0.5
	E-Awareness of End User	0.5	0.5	0.5
	F-Technological Development	1	1	1
	G-Participation of Skilled Manpower	1	1	1
Tidal	A-Indigenous Manufacturing and Development	1	1	1
	B-Resource Potential	1	1	1
	C-Influential Policy Implication	1	0.5	1
	D-User Subsidy	1	0.5	1
	E-Awareness of End User	0.5	0.5	1
	F-Technological Development	0.5	1	1
	G-Participation of Skilled Manpower	1	1	1

The above scores were used to obtain average credit scores for each resource option and the results were obtained as shown in table II. Aggregation of the scores from each

growth factor was done to deduce the final results for each resource option.

Table II: Combine Scores for each Resource Option

Resource	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	Average Credit Score
Solar	2.5	3	2.5	3	3	2.5	3	2.79
Wind	2	2	2	1.5	2.5	3	1.5	2.07
Waste-to-Energy	2.5	2.5	3	2	1.5	3	3	2.50
Tidal	3	3	2.5	2.5	2	2.5	3	2.64

Solar stood at first rank with a score of 2.79. It performs better in resource potential available, user subsidies, and technological development. Tidal stood second in the overall ranking with a score of 2.64. It performs better in resource potential, indigenous manufacturing and development, and participation of skilled manpower. Waste-to-energy stood third in the overall ranking with a

score of 2.50 as it has performed marginally better in participation of skilled labor, technological development, and resource potential on categories. Influential policy measures taken by the government in large cities are also an important factor that has supplemented the highest scores for this resource. The wind stood fourth with a credit

score of 2.07 as it performs low in user subsidy and influential policy implications.

IV. CONCLUSION

Our result concludes that solar followed by tidal, waste-to-energy, and wind are the best options that should be adapted to resolve energy crises in large cities as they will benefit our society largely. With proper policy implications, abundant solar resources in the country could be used as it is environmentally friendly and less expensive. It is a good option for usage in low-income households on an individual basis. By proper mitigation of policies, two main issues of large cities' waste management and energy shortages could be resolved. Available tidal resources in the country should be exploited to benefit the society largely. By proper adaptation of policies, we can benefit our society by planting waste-to-energy plants as it resolves unemployment issues, waste management, and energy scarcity. Wind energy is also a good option for large cities, especially where wind corridors are available near the coastal belt. It can supplement cheap energy in place of expensive fossil fuels and could be used to supply the energy needs of large populations in densely populated cities. Pakistan has abundant green energy resources which could be utilized by the formation of a proper policy roadmap and mitigation of policy pathways to overcome the hazardous dependence on fossil fuels for energy requirements.

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Authors Contributions

Both the authors; Leezna Saleem, and Intikhab Ulfat, equally contributed to this study.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest and confirm that this work is original and not plagiarized from any other source, i.e., electronic or print media. The information obtained from all of the sources is properly recognized and cited below.

Data Availability Statement

The testing data is available in this paper.

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